

Synthesis of α -naphthol and β -naphthol annulated heterocycles : Regioselective heterocyclization of 2-allylnaphthalene-1-ol and 1-allylnaphthalene-2-ol

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Abstract : 2-Allylnaphthalene-1-ol (**1a**) and 1-allylnaphthalene-2-ol (**1b**) undergo regioselective heterocyclization to give 5-*exo*-trig cyclized products **2a** or **2b** on treatment with pyridine hydrotribromide (**3h**); or hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide (**2h**); or elemental bromine in CHCl_3 (7 h); or *N*-bromosuccinimide in acetonitrile at 0–5 °C (1 h), respectively. The 5-*exo*-trig cyclization route is further supported by the conversion of **2a** or **2b** to dehydrobromination product **3a** or **3b** respectively in presence of alcoholic KOH under reflux (30 min).

Keywords : Regioselective, heterocyclization, 5-*exo*-trig, *N*-bromosuccinimide, dehydrobromination.

Introduction

Various types of reactions have been utilized to-date for the formation of C–C bonds and for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds and their applications for the formation of the pyran and furan rings in heterocycles and their mechanistic aspects have been studied in detail.

Compounds containing naphthalene moiety have been reported to show a variety of biological activities including antimicrobial activities^{1,2}, HIV-1 integrase inhibitory effect³, anti-inflammatory activity⁴, inhibition of protein tyrosine kinases² and inactivation of enveloped viruses⁵.

ortho-Allyl naphthols are versatile intermediates in the synthesis of potentially biologically active compounds like 1,4-naphthoquinones^{6a} and anthracyclines^{6b,c}. The [3,3] sigmatropic shift (Claisen rearrangement) of allyl aryl ethers can furnish convenient access to *ortho*-allyl naphthols⁷. Although the Claisen rearrangement is the efficient synthetic route for the preparation of *ortho*-allyl naphthols, it usually requires high temperatures⁶ and therefore synthetic methodologies involving rare earth triflates as catalysts for the Claisen rearrangement have also been found to be extremely useful^{8,9}. Microwave assisted Claisen rearrangement of *ortho*-allylated β -naphthol was also reported¹⁰ using microwave irradiation conditions

without using any solvent and this method has the advantages over conventional conditions¹¹ in various aspects.

Previously we have carried out¹² the heterocyclization of 2-(cyclohex-2'-enyl)-5,5-dimethyl-3-hydroxycyclohex-2-enone using different reagents. The heterocyclization using pyridine hydrotribromide¹³, mercuric acetate¹⁴ and hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide¹⁵ are well documented in literatures. Some of the recent works reported so far include the heterocyclization of 3-cyclohex-2'-enyl-4-hydroxycoumarin¹⁶, 3-allyl-4 hydroxy[1]benzopyran-2-ones^{17,18}, *o*-cyclohex-2-enylanilines¹⁹, 2-allyl-4,5,6-tribromo-3-hydroxybenzoate²⁰. With these facts in our mind we have also decided to carry out the heterocyclization of 2-allylnaphthalene-1-ol (**1a**) and 1-allylnaphthalene-2-ol (**1b**) by using different reagents. Here we report the results.

Results and discussion

We directed our research activity towards the synthesis of different heterocycles derived from 2-allylnaphthalene-1-ol (**1a**) and 1-allylnaphthalene-2-ol (**1b**). Compounds **1** were synthesized according to the published procedure²¹ starting from the allylation of the corresponding α -naphthol and β -naphthol to get *o*-allylated products and this is followed by their Claisen rearrangement.

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Scheme 1. Condition A : (a) PyHBr_3 , 0–5 °C, 3 h; or (b) hexamethylene tetraminehydrotribromide, 0–5 °C, 2 h; or (c) Br_2 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, and then at 60 °C for 6 h or (d) NBS, CH_3CN , 0–5 °C, 1 h; Condition B : KOH, EtOH, reflux, 30 min.

We considered three different routes for the heterocyclizations. First the substrate **1a** was treated with one equivalent of pyridine hydrotribromide and hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide separately for 2–3 h to give a new product. This new product was characterized as compound **2a** (Scheme 1, Table 1) from its elemental analysis and spectral data. In the same way **1b** also afforded **2b** (Scheme 2, Table 1).

Table 1

Sr. No.	SM	Product	Reaction condition	Yield (%)
1.	1(a)	2(a)	(i) PyHBr_3 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, 3 h	70
2.	1(a)	2(a)	(ii) Hexamethylene tetramine hydrotribromide, CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, 2 h	74
3.	1(a)	2(a)	(iii) Br_2 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, and then at 60 °C for 6 h	64
4.	1(a)	2(a)	(iv) NBS, CH_3CN , 0–5 °C, 1 h	85
5.	1(b)	2(b)	(i) PyHBr_3 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, 3 h	72
6.	1(b)	2(b)	(ii) Hexamethylene tetramine hydrotribromide, CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, 2 h	79
7.	1(b)	2(b)	(iii) Br_2 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, and then at 60 °C for 6 h	60
8.	1(b)	2(b)	(iv) NBS, CH_3CN , 0–5 °C, 1 h	89

68 °C (Scheme 1, Table 1) and **2b** (60%) m.p. 92 °C (Scheme 2, Table 1) respectively. The compounds were characterized from its elemental analyses and spectroscopic data.

We finally decided to treat the substrate **1a** and **1b** separately with *N*-bromosuccinimide in dry acetonitrile at 0–5 °C for 1 h to get a gummy mass. The respective crude gummy mass, was purified using SiO_2 column chromatography with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluant, to furnish product **2a** (85%) or **2b** (89%) respectively (Schemes 1, 2; Table 1).

In all the above cases there are two probabilities for C-allylic phenolic systems (**1a** and **1b**) to undergo heterocyclization involving either 5-*exo*-trig or 6-*endo*-trig mode, 5-*exo*-trig mode is more common. In our present study, we also got 2-(bromomethyl)-2,3-dihydro-1H-naphtho[1,2-*b*]furan (**2a**) or 2-(bromomethyl)-1,2-dihydro-naphtho[2,1-*b*]furan (**2b**) involving 5-*exo*-trig heterocyclization of **1a** or **1b** respectively. The formation of five membered heterocycle is confirmed by dehydrobromination of **2a** or **2b** with alcoholic KOH under reflux affording **3a** (80%) or **3b** (84%) respectively (Table 2).

Scheme 2. Condition A : (a) PyHBr_3 , 0–5 °C, 3 h; or (b) hexamethylene tetraminehydrotribromide, 0–5 °C, 2 h; or (c) Br_2 , CHCl_3 , 0–5 °C, and then at 60 °C for 6 h or (d) NBS, CH_3CN , 0–5 °C, 1 h; Condition B : KOH, EtOH, reflux, 30 min.

We, then, treated our substrate **1a** and **1b** separately with elemental bromine in chloroform with constant stirring at 0–5 °C for 6 h to give white solids **2a** (64%) m.p.

If the 6-*endo*-trig mode was operative the heterocyclization of **1a** would afford **4a** in place of **2a** and dehydrobromination would produce **5a** in place of **3a** via

Sr. No.	SM	Product	Reaction condition	Yield (%)
1.	2(a)	3(a)	KOH, EtOH, reflux, 30 min	80
2.	2(a)	3(a)	KOH, EtOH, reflux, 30 min	84

the cyclic bromonium ion (A) (Scheme 3). From the study of ^1H NMR of **3a**, it is clear that δ 2.53 (s, 3H), is due to the methyl proton and appearance of a singlet at δ 6.84 is due to the proton of the type =CH inside the 5-membered ring. The remaining six protons at δ 7.41–7.68 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.92 (d, J 8.1 Hz, 1H, ArH), and 8.06 (d, J 8.1 Hz, 1H, ArH) are due to the presence of six aromatic protons.

Scheme 3. Mechanistic interpretation of the cyclized product (**2a**).

Therefore, the alternative structure **4a** and **5a** through 6-endo-trig pathway was ruled out on the basis of chemical and spectroscopic evidences. The same would happen for the cyclisation of **1b** also (Scheme 2).

It may be concluded that the heterocyclizations of 2-allylnaphthalen-1-ol (**1a**) and 1-allylnaphthalen-2-ol (**1b**) are found to be regioselective with reagents such as *N*-bromosuccinimide, elemental bromine, pyridinehydrotribromide or hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide, to give **2a** or **2b** respectively.

Experimental

All the reagents were obtained from commercial

sources and used as received. Except methanol (which was HPLC-grade), the remaining solvents were dried and distilled before use.

Elemental analyses and Mass spectra (ESI+) were performed at the Indian Institute of Chemical Biology, Kolkata. IR spectra were recorded on KBr discs on a Perkin-Elmer L120-000A apparatus (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}). Routine ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DPX-400 MHz instrument at 298 K. The chemical shifts (δ) are given in ppm and the coupling constants (J) in Hz. In all cases the solvent for the NMR experiments was CDCl_3 (99.9%) and the references were SiMe_4 [for ^1H and $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR experiments]. Silica gel [(60–

120, 230–400 mesh), SRL, India] was used for chromatographic separation. Silica gel G [E. Marck (India)] and Silica gel 60F 254 [E. Marck (Germany)] were used for TLC. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction boiling between 60 and 80 °C.

Pyridine hydrotribromide or hexamethylenetetramine hydrotribromide mediated cyclization of compound 1a or 1b :

A solution of compound (**1a** or **1b**, 2.0 mmol) in CHCl_3 (50 mL) was stirred with solid pyridine hydrotribromide (0.45 g, 2.0 mmol) at 0–5 °C for 3 h. The CHCl_3 layer was washed with 5% Na_2CO_3 solution (3×10 mL), then

with water (3 × 25 mL) and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of CHCl₃ left the crude residues. They were purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluant to give product **2a** or **2b** respectively.

Cyclization of compound 1a or 1b by elemental bromine :

Elemental bromine (0.25 g, 1.5 mmol) in chloroform (15 mL) was added slowly to a well-stirred solution of compound **1a** or **1b** (1.5 mmol) in chloroform (10 mL) at 0–5 °C. Stirring was continued for an additional period of 5 h at 0–5 °C. After the reaction was over (as monitored by TLC) it was extracted with chloroform. The CHCl₃ layer was washed with 5% Na₂CO₃ solution (2 × 10 mL), then with water (2 × 25 mL) and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of CHCl₃ left a crude mass. This was purified by column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as eluant. From comparison of TLC, m.p., mixed m.p. and super imposable IR this product was found to be identical with product **2a** or **2b** respectively obtained from the reaction of compound **1a** or **1b** with PyHBr₃ or C₆H₁₂N₄HBr₃.

N-Bromosuccinimide mediated cyclization of compound 1a or 1b :

Compound **1a** (1 mmol) or **1b** (1 mmol) was dissolved in acetonitrile solution at 0–5 °C and *N*-bromosuccinimide (1 mmol) was added at a time. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 1 h on a magnetic stirrer at 0–5 °C. It was stirred for an additional period of 15 min at room temperature. On completion of the reaction (as monitored by TLC) acetonitrile solution was removed from the reaction mixture under reduced pressure. The residual mass was extracted with chloroform and washed with 5% NaHCO₃ solution (3 × 25 mL), water (2 × 25 mL) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The residual mass after removal of the solvent was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl-acetate (9 : 1) as eluant to give product **2a** (85%) or **2b** (89%) respectively.

Spectroscopic data :

2-(Bromomethyl)-2,3-dihydronaphtho[1,2-b]furan (2a) : m.p. 68 °C; IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 3056, 2922, 1759, 1594, 1508, 1435, 1398, 1354, 1082, 757, 654; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.25–3.31 (dd, *J* 15.6, 6.6 Hz, 1H),

3.51–3.60 (m, 2H), 3.70 (dd, *J* 15.6, 10.4 Hz, 1H), 5.17–5.24 (m, 1H), 7.47–7.60 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.95 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.16 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 34.4, 35.1, 82.0, 113.0, 119.5, 121.3, 121.9, 126.2, 126.5, 127.2, 127.3, 131.7, 154.4; *m/z* 262 (M⁺) (Found : C, 59.56; H, 4.04. C₁₃H₁₁BrO requires : C, 59.34; H, 4.21%).

2-(Bromomethyl)-1,2-dihydronaphtho[2,1-b]furan (2b) : m.p. 92 °C; IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 3058, 2919, 1632, 1580, 1521, 1445, 1374, 1351, 1242, 1058, 968, 808, 746; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.29–3.35 (dd, *J* 15.6, 6.4 Hz, 2H), 3.51–3.65 (m, 2H), 5.10–5.18 (m, 1H), 7.1 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.28–7.32 (m, 1H, ArH), 7.43–7.47 (m, 1H, ArH), 7.55 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.67 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.79 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 33.5, 34.8, 82.0, 112.0, 117.4, 122.7, 123.2, 126.9, 128.8, 129.3, 129.4, 130.7, 156.6; *m/z* 262 (M⁺) (Found : C, 59.45; H, 4.34. C₁₃H₁₁BrO requires : C, 59.34; H, 4.21%).

Dehydrobromination of compound 2a or 2b :

Compound **2a** (1 mmol) or **2b** (1 mmol) was dissolved in rectified spirit (5 mL) and potassium hydroxide (0.056 g, 1 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 30 min. After the reaction was over (as detected by TLC), rectified spirit was removed and the residue was extracted with dichloromethane and washed with water (2 × 25 mL) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The residual mass after removal of the solvent was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl-acetate (9 : 1) as eluant to give product **3a** (80%) or **3b** (84%) respectively.

2-Methylnaphtho[1,2-b]furan (3a) : Gummy mass; IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (KBr) : 2950, 2918, 2852, 1603, 1574, 1437, 1384, 1315, 1173, 1082, 938, 815, 744, 686; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.56 (s, 3H, CH₃), 6.48 (s, 1H), 7.41–7.62 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.91 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.24 (d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 1H, ArH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 14.1, 103.6, 119.2, 119.6, 121.1, 122.9, 124.3, 124.5, 126.0, 128.2, 130.7, 149.8, 154.5; *m/z* 182 (M⁺) (Found : C, 85.77; H, 5.42. C₁₃H₁₀O requires : C, 85.69; H, 5.53%).

2-Methylnaphtho[2,1-b]furan (3b) : m.p. 60–62 °C; IR $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ (KBr) : 2949, 2920, 1629, 1578, 1441, 1384, 1210, 1165, 1022, 939, 801, 739, 688; ¹H NMR

(400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.53 (s, 3H, CH₃), 6.84 (s, 1H), 7.41–7.68 (m, 4H, ArH), 7.92 (d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.06 (d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 1H, ArH); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 14.2, 101.7, 112.0, 123.4, 123.7, 124.1, 124.2, 125.8, 127.3, 128.6, 130.1, 151.8, 154.6; HRMS : [M+H]⁺ 183.0815 (Found : C, 85.82; H, 5.71. C₁₃H₁₀O requires : C, 85.69; H, 5.53%).

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References

1. S. Goksu, M. T. Uguz, H. Ozdemir and H. A. Secen, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 199.
2. T. R. Burke, M. Fesen, A. Mazumder, J. Yung, A. M. Carothers, D. Grunberger, J. Driscoll, Y. Pommier and K. John, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 4171.
3. M. Huang, S. Wu, J. Wang, C. Lin, S. Lu, L. Liao and A. Shen, *Drug Dev. Res.*, 2003, **60**, 261.
4. T. R. Burke, R. Lim, V. E. Marquez, B. H. Li, J. B. Bolen, I. Stefanova and I. D. Horak, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1993, **36**, 425.
5. F. Kasermann and C. Kempf, *Antiviral Research*, 1998, **38**, 55.
6. (a) L. F. Fieser, W. P. Campbell and E. M. Fry, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2206; (b) I. Takahashi, A. Nomura and H. Kitajima, *Synth. Commun.*, 1990, **20**, 1569; (c) S. Kotha and K. Mandal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 2585.
7. For a recent review on the Claisen rearrangement, see : A. M. M. Castro, *Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **104**, 2939.
8. For a review on rare-earth triflates, see : (a) S. Kobayashi, M. Sugiura, H. Kitagawa and W. W.-L. Lam, *Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **102**, 2227; (b) G. V. M. Sharma, A. Ilangoan, P. Sreenivas and A. K. Mahalingam, *Synlett*, 2000, 615.
9. T. Ollevier and T. M. Mwene-Mbeja, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 4051.
10. (a) S. Kotha and K. Mandal, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 1391; (b) S. Kotha, K. Mandal, A. Tiwari and S. M. Mobin, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2006, **12**, 8024.
11. J. Green and D. McHale, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1964, 1801.
12. K. C. Majumdar, S. K. Samanta and P. K. Basu, *Synth. Commun.*, 2003, **33**, 679.
13. (a) K. C. Majumdar, U. K. Kundu and S. K. Ghosh, *Org. Lett.*, 2002, **4**, 2629; (b) K. C. Majumdar and A. K. Kundu, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1995 **73**, 1727; (c) K. C. Majumdar, P. K. Choudhury and M. Nethaji, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 5927.
14. K. C. Majumdar, R. N. De and S. Saha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 1207; (b) K. C. Majumdar and U. Das, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1996, **74**, 1592.
15. K. C. Majumdar, P. Chatterjee and A. K. Kundu, *Synth. Commun.*, 1996, **26**, 893.
16. K. C. Majumdar and S. Sarkar, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 8501.
17. K. C. Majumdar, P. K. Basu and B. Roy, *Synth. Commun.*, 2003, **33**, 3621.
18. (a) K. C. Majumdar, A. Biswas and P. P. Mukhopadhyay, *Can. J. Chem.*, 2005, **83**, 2046; (b) K. C. Majumdar, A. Biswas and P. P. Mukhopadhyay, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 2881.
19. K. C. Majumdar, U. K. Kundu, U. Das, N. K. Jana and B. Roy, *Can. J. Chem.*, 2005, **83**, 63.
20. F. A. Khan and L. Soma, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 85.
21. (a) S. H. Reich, M. Melnick, M. J. Pino, M. A. M. Fuhry, A. J. Trippe, K. Appelt, J. F. Davies II, B.-W. Wu and L. Musick, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **39**, 2781.

